

GENDER EQUALITY IN EMPLOYMENT IN KAZAKHSTAN.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5914121>

Bakhtiyorova Gulnoza

*HR Specialist at Banking & Finance Academy
(Tashkent, Uzbekistan)*

Abstract: *Women play an essential role in promoting economic and social development in a country, so it is crucial to increase job opportunities for women. However, there is still complexity and ambiguity in terms of equal work opportunities for men and women. In Central Asia, it is mostly women who suffer from unequal opportunities at work and in life due to culture, society, religion, economics and politics. Women's contributions in the economic and social sphere are devalued and underestimated. There are, however, several strategies to strengthen women in order to make their rights equal with men, especially in the labour market in Central Asian regions. This article will discuss about the gender inequality in labour markets in Kazakhstan and the change in the role of women over the last years.*

Keywords: *Human Development Index, Kazakhstan, gender gap, women, employment, gender equality.*

Introduction

Kazakhstan is the world's ninth largest country and the biggest landlocked country in the world although the population is around 19 million people. Human development Index is the level of development in three areas: health, education and a standard of living. The Human Development Index is considered to be low in Kazakhstan in the global perspective. In 2021, the country was 51st in the list with the Human Development Index of 0.825. Slightly more than a country's total population constitute women, but their contribution to the economy is lower than the contribution of their male counterparts. In terms of gender gap ranking, Kazakhstan was N60 among 149 countries in 2018, and it continued to deteriorate reaching N72 in 2020. Furthermore, the amount of benefit that women can get from the economic development of any nation depends on the position of women in the labour market. Additionally, according to the study conducted by International Monetary Fund, the more the women participate in the workforce, the higher the economic growth and the welfare of the nation. In this way, when the participation of women in the labour market in Central Asia and Europe increases, economic wellbeing goes up by about 1%.

Methods

This is both the qualitative and quantitative study that employs the literature review analysis as its main technique. The primary data has been collected from research papers, published journals and official websites for statistical data. The statistical data has been collected with regards to the share of women in the labour market and their contribution to it. In terms of qualitative study, certain terms have been defined using the definitions given by official sites and books.

Main findings

In Kazakhstan, the percentage of women participation in the economic activities in 2018 was 64.8%, which was 11.1 % lower than that of men. The unemployment rate among women also remained higher as compared to men, at 5.4 % for women in 2018 while for men 4.3%. The distribution of genders in different sectors in the economy is also very distinguished. The highest number of women are employed in education, health care and service sectors, almost 70%. In 2008, the gender pay gap in Kazakhstan was large, totalling 36%. Women's salaries constituted 65.8% of men's salaries. The gender gaps in labour remuneration differed with age groups, such as 36.7% within 35-44 years, 35% (45-54 years) and within the age groups of 65 and above and 25 and below were 25.3% and 16.9% respectively. The gender pay gaps differ as per the types of occupations as well. For instance, women's earnings in the administrative and support services are higher than men's by more than 95%. In health and social services, the wage gaps are minor, where women's income is 93.3% of that of men. In the remaining areas such as the arts and entertainment sectors, women's salaries are 50.4% of men's salaries, in the technical and scientific fields 64%.

Results

The government of Kazakhstan implements certain technical cooperation activities to increase women's participation and equal opportunities in the country. According to the laws of the country, there is no discrimination between the genders in any field, but these laws are not always practised. The absence of formal equality means that women are treated lower than men, especially in the labour market they are paid less than men for the same job they performed.

Conclusion

Although women have higher educational qualifications than men, their employment opportunities in the labour market are considerably limited. Legal barriers mean that women encounter discrimination when applying for male-dominated jobs and the gender gap remains prevalent in the country. This affects the overall participation of women and youngsters in the economy of Kazakhstan. In addition, gender equality ensures the balanced economic growth and stability in the country. Besides, equal participation of genders in the labour market does more than this. This means that working women become independent not only

financially but also within the household. They greatly contribute to the distribution of various resources at home. Therefore, it is the fundamental responsibility of the government to ensure to practice the laws to control the gender equality and regulate this practice in every field.

REFERENCES:

1. Asian Development Bank. 2013. "Gender Equality and the Labor Market. Cambodia, Kazakhstan and the Philippines." URL: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/31167/gender-equality-cambodia-philippines-kazakhstan.pdf>
2. Alshanskaya A. "How Much, Where and How Do Women Earn in Kazakhstan?" Central Asian Bureau for Analytical reporting. URL: <https://cabar.asia/en/how-much-where-and-how-do-women-earn-in-kazakhstan>
3. European Bank for Reconstruction and Development. "Towards Equal Opportunities for All in Kazakhstan's Energy and Mining Sectors". <https://www.ebrd.com/what-we-do/country-snapshot/kazakhstan-inclusion-case-study>
4. Gender regime and Women's Employment. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/viewer.html?pdfurl=https%3A%2F%2Flink.springer.com%2Fcontent%2Fpdf%2F10.1057%2Fs41294-021-00173-0.pdf&cflen=653858&chunk=true
5. Klaveren M., Tijdens K. "An Overview of Women's Work and Employment in Kazakhstan". Decision for Life MDG3 Project Country Report No.10. 2010. URL: https://www.ituc-csi.org/IMG/pdf/Country_Report_No10-Kazakhstan_EN.pdf
6. Khazmina Z. et al. 2020. "Is it possible to achieve gender equality in Kazakhstan: Focus on Employment and Social Protection". URL: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1358229120927904>
7. Mynbayeva J. "Women in Kazakhstan. Wonder Foundation Insight Report". <https://wonderfoundation.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/Women-in-Kazakhstan-Wonder-Foundation-Insight-Report-Digital.pdf>